

Section
(Meta)data,
Terminologies,
Provenance

Working Group Charter
**Ontology harmonization
and mapping**

Name of the working group

Ontology harmonization and mapping

Acronym

section-metadata-wg-onto

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1. Motivation

In order to achieve semantic interoperability and facilitate the implementation of the FAIR principles, several interrelated task areas have been identified that can benefit from cross-NFDI coordination. These include the harmonization and/or mapping of terminologies and the delivery of “FAIR” terminologies, to be used in connected domain-specific knowledge graphs, based on interoperable technical frameworks. Harmonization refers to finding an agreement on a common terminology, whereas mapping refers to an “agreement to disagree”, while using a well-defined interface between terminologies. In the context of harmonization we refer to the mapping/alignment of OWL ontologies, SKOS vocabularies, and or other controlled vocabularies and thesauri. This could cover for example DCAT versus schema.org or PROV versus BFO. This is not equivalent to the mapping/alignment/crosswalks of metadata schema, which we consider as being covered by the Task Force Metadata.

Each consortium in the NFDI comes with their own set of terminologies, at different stages of maturity, and at different levels of FAIRness. Accordingly, ontologies and controlled vocabularies evolve in different time-frames and for different purposes. They are prone to have conceptual overlaps and – as in natural language – there are different ways of expressing the same concept. Mappings between equivalent representations of the same concept are thus essential for the federation of data that are structured with domain ontologies. The creation of formal, machine-readable mappings and their metadata needs to be guided by common standards. Additionally, the use of upper-level ontologies and the re-use of terms from existing terminologies need to be promoted. In addition to mapping (near) equivalent and semantically overlapping terms, disambiguation between terms “overloaded” with different meanings in different disciplines is another key task.

2. Objectives

A. Collaborating Internationally

Achieve cross-domain interoperability between NFDI and other international infrastructures (EOSC/RDA), by participating in or exchange with similar external working groups and task forces. Such interoperability will be realized by provision of linkages and crosswalks between terminologies, ontologies and domain-specific knowledge graphs. As part of an identification process existing EOSC/RDA recommendations will be analyzed to endorse them or to adapt them if needed. Recommendations that are addressing other objectives (e.g. objective B) will be passed along. Relevant mappings, at best in a processable format like SSSOM and JSKOS, indexed in official shared registries like Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR), will be collected. The experience gained will be summarized in a recommendation that explains how to find existing external mappings and crosswalks.

Specific Tasks

- Gain overview of organisational structure, working units, and recommendations
- Launch a query to all those involved in our WG to find out who is active in which working units (Low Level approach, amend table at the end of the charter to add who is in which WG)
- Connect to relevant working units

- Get draft/final of recommended terminology from relevant groups
- Identify equivalent ontologies in NFDI
- Evaluate and somehow serve existing mappings, Overlap with objective B & C.
 - Generic mappings useful for more NFDI consortia should be curated and provisioned by the WG. Overlap with C
 - How to publish/serve mappings/crosswalks overlap with B
- Assess existing approaches to achieve “cross-domain knowledge sharing”, like CDIF, DCAT-AP, & Schema.org
 - Assist the Task Force Metadata of the NFDI Section (Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance in defining a minimum information standard for NFDI data publications required for semantic interoperability.

B. Assessing Mapping & Alignment Standards

Assess and evaluate existing standards and tools for creating, validating/benchmarking, documenting and publishing terminology mappings and alignments, such as SSSOM, OAEI, and RML, to determine their applicability and suitability for the NFDI context. This assessment will inform the development of guidelines and recommendations for implementing these standards within the NFDI, including any necessary adaptations or extensions to meet the specific needs of the NFDI community. The ultimate goal is to produce a set of guidelines that provide clear instructions and best practices for NFDI members on how to implement these standards and leverage the resulting mappings.

Specific Tasks

- Find instructions and have specialist discussions on ontology mapping & alignment from the field of computer science.
- Assess and discuss how to use SSSOM in NFDI.
- Assess and discuss how to use OAEI in NFDI.
- Assess and discuss how to publish one's mappings?
 - Should it be in the source file of a semantic artefact or in a separate file? If the latter, how should the two be connected and where should the mapping files be published?
 - Indexing mappings in a NFDI mapping registry.
 - Recommend implementation in NFDI that is somehow connected to the [mapping commons initiative](#).
 - Collaborate with the TS4NFDI project which is working on the technical implementation.
- Discuss and agree on a NFDI metadata standard for a mapping set

C. NFDI-wide Collaboration on Use Cases

The working group aims to provide a clearing house of experiences from within the NFDI in mapping and harmonizing terminologies. We will collect and evaluate mapping experiences, maintain communication with use cases – inviting NFDI participants to exchange their experience and/or surveying them as necessary – and evaluate them in the context of other objectives. The goal is to provide clear examples for others who are attempting mappings and harmonization but also to define improvements that enhance interoperability and reduce mapping costs in the future. In contrast to objective A that considers a more international perspective, this objective focuses more on NFDI wide internal exchange and discussions. The insights and conclusions

obtained in objective C will be shared as part of objective A on a broader international level.

Specific Tasks

- Collect, present, discuss & solve NFDI specific mapping/harmonization use cases. (E.g. CIDOC-CRM & NFDIcore mapping is needed)
- Define and use the WG communication channels (regular calls, email list, Rocket chat) to:
 - inform and discuss with the NFDI terminology community updates on a specific terminology development in a specific consortium (upcoming new releases & possible breaking changes) in a common way
 - enable community participation in specific terminology development projects.
- Document discussions and their outcomes and feed this back into other channels if necessary (e.g. RDA/EOSC working groups / task forces)

D. NFDI's Best Practices for Terminology Development & Publishing

Create and continuously update a collaborative resource that captures evolving best practices, standards, and tools that should be considered when tackling terminology development projects within the NFDI. This living document will: *Provide* a glossary of key terms and definitions in the field of terminology engineering; *Offer* practical how-to's and guidelines for applying international standards; *Introduce* common and open tools and approaches, including ODK, MOD-profiles, design patterns and terminology hosting, to facilitate and harmonize terminology development; *Document* and share best practices and examples of successful terminology development projects, after they have been informed and discussed within the working group via the regular communication channels; Ultimately, *Serve* as a living document, regularly updated to reflect new developments and advancements in the field of terminology engineering.

Specific Tasks

- Set up a collaborative/living document: decide which publication and hosting infrastructure is best suited to the collaborative and updating nature of the resource (e.g. GitHub pages, Wiki software, Read the Docs...).
- Assess and translate the OBO principles, available community standards, tools and best practices, into practical action points to facilitate decision making and harmonization on terminology development issues. This includes agreement on (but is not limited to) following topics:
 - tools (ODK)
 - have a list of repos that use ODK for NFDI associated ontology development
 - term re-use or import,
 - modularity,
 - formats (RDF, OWL, JSON-LD,...),
 - mapping standards (SSSOM, JSKOS),
 - terminology metadata schema ([MOD](#)-profile)
 - design patterns,
 - terminology hosting.

- Create a glossary of the most important terms in the field of terminology engineering to make it clear we are talking about the same things.
- Continuous integration of the results of the previous objective tasks for this objective into the living document.

E. NFDI's Used Terminologies

Collect which consortium reuses, develops, or evaluates which terminologies in a common machine actionable manner that allows further analyses regarding common needs and synergies. Use this collection as a basis for our work and recommendations associated with the other objectives.

Specific Tasks

- Provide a way for each consortium to report which existing terminologies are being reused, developed or considered for reuse.
 - Decide if the existing Google Sheet is sufficient, or if other technical means are better (e.g. collections in the [Semantic Farm](#) or FAIRsharing).
 - Make sure such collections are indexed in the TS4NFDI project.
- Decide which parameters must/should be reported.
- Collaboration with the TS4NFDI project regarding possible requirements.
- Evaluate used upper-level & domain-agnostic vocabularies as basis for mapping use case discussions (input to objectives C & D).

3. Work Plan

Previous work of the WG between 2023 - 2025 was reported on in a progress report.¹ Ongoing tasks are organized via issues collected in the GitHub repository (<http://github.com/nfdi-de/section-metadata-wg-onto>). Issues are tagged with the specific objective they refer to (i.e. Collaborating Internationally) so that they can be addressed by the relevant group members. Due to the voluntary nature of this working group, the versioning control and issue addendums that Github provides is particularly valuable, as it allows group members to easily follow along with task developments and contribute at a later time, even if they could not be directly involved in initial progress.

Currently (Q2/2026), the group is working to publish recommendations and documentation for each objective and will then build a consensus based on these recommendations. Earlier this year, terminology collections for all NFDI consortia were curated in the Semantic Farm. In the coming months, these will be analysed to better elucidate the NFDI terminology landscape.

4. Represented Consortia

Name	Consortium	Role in WG	Email
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¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19237888> published March 26, 2026

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5. Adoption Plan

Once concrete needs for harmonization and/or mapping of terminologies have been identified, and subgroups tasked with deliberating the actual changes and amendments to ontologies and vocabularies have been set up, feedback into the consortia and the scientific communities they represent is going to be crucial for the success of the WG.

Given the NFDI's bottom-up approach, the consortia are the forums for discussion which terminologies should be used and how they should be modified and adopted. This WG is going to support the consortia in these decision processes, by providing expertise and feedback from the NFDI as a whole.

Adoption plans for individual cases of terminology development may differ, depending on the state of the art. They are going to be agreed on a case-by-case basis, guided by FAIR principles and Good Scientific Practice as overarching principles.

6. Connected to other NFDI working groups

- Search & Harvesting
- Taskforce Metadata
- Semantic Interoperability: Terminology Services
- Cookbooks, Guidance, Best Practices
- Knowledge Graphs
- Working Group "Training Infrastructures" of Section Training & Education
- Working Group "Data Integration" of section "Common Infrastructures"

7. Connected to other working groups outside NFDI

- EOSC Task force [Semantic Interoperability](#)
- RDA [Data Granularity WG](#) ?
- RDA [FAIR Mappings Working Group](#)
- W3C [Web Ontology WG](#)
- The [Ontology Matching Community](#) and the [Ontology Alignment Evaluation Initiative](#) (OAEI)
- The [Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology](#) Foundry (OBO)

- [Data for History Consortium](#)
- [CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model](#) Special Interest Group
- [LIDO Working Group](#)
- [Minimum Record Recommendation Working Group](#)
- Project [Anwendung Interoperabler Metadatenstandards](#) (AIMS)
- The FAIR Digital Objects Forum
- WorldFAIR-Project [CDIF](#)